

Cultural and chemical methods to prevent lodging and stabilize yield of a tall indica rice

J. S. Urkurkar, junior scientist, and B. R. Chandravanshi, senior scientist, Zonal Agricultural Research Station (Rice Zone), Raipur, M. P., India

Safri (BD200), a long-duration, tall indica rice, is popular in the Chhatisgarh region of Central India. It lodges severely because of excessive vegetative growth, particularly with heavy N fertilization, which limits yield.

In 1980 wet season, in a silt loam soil, we conducted a field trial to determine cultural and chemical methods to reduce lodging and increase yield stability. The experiment was in a randomized block design with four replications. Forty-five-day-old seedlings were planted at 15- x 15-cm plant spacing on 8 Aug 1980. Treatments are summarized in the table. Data were collected on plant height and rice grain yield.

Plant height was not influenced by in-

Effect of chemical and cultural treatments on plant height and grain yield of the tall indica Bd 200. Raipur, India.

Treatment	Plant height (cm)			Grain yield (t/ha)		
	Fertility ^a		Mean	Fertility		Mean
	F ₁	F ₂		F ₁	F ₂	
Control	133	140	136	4.1	4.2	4.1
Leaf topping at maximum tillering	132	127	130	3.9	4.0	3.9
Cycocel (40 ppm) spray at mid-tillering	123	127	125	4.0	4.8	4.4
Cycocel (40 ppm) spray at maximum tillering	129	131	130	3.9	4.1	4.0
Double transplanting 25 d after first transplanting	126	122	124	3.4	3.3	3.3
Mean	128	129		3.9	4.1	
CD (5%)						
Lodging treatments	6 cm			0.4 t/ha		
Fertility	ns			ns		
Interaction	9 cm			0.5 t/ha		

^a Fertility: F₁ = 80, 13, 17 kg NPK/ha. F₂ = 80, 26, 33 kg NPK/ha.

creasing P or K levels, but was markedly affected by different cultural and chemical treatments. All treatments reduced plant height over the control. Double transplanting reduced plant height most, and also reduced final yield. Cycocel sprayed at 40 ppm at mid-

tillering reduced plant height and plant vigor, and increased grain yield 6% over the control.

Cycocel, with optimum fertilizer application, helped minimize vegetative growth, thereby diverting the physiological activities toward grain production. □

Response of rice varieties to applied nitrogen in saline soils

C. Jashim, U. Ahmed, and K. U. Ahmed, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI) Regional Station, Sonagazi, Bangladesh

Bangladesh has about 0.8 million ha of saline land with low N content. We studied the effect of different levels of applied N on growth and yield of direct-seeded (dibbled), rainfed BR9 rice at the BRRI farm in Sonagazi in 1983 (summer).

Effect of different levels of applied N on growth and yield of direct-seeded (dibbled) BR9 grown in saline soils, BRRI. ^a

Treatment (kg N/ha)	Plant height (cm)	Panicles/m ²	Tillers/hill	Yield (t/ha)
0	106	157 c	5 c	1.4 c
20	110	204 bc	6 bc	2.2 b
40	117	256 ab	8 b	2.3 b
60	120	316 a	11 a	3.4 a
80	126	330 a	12 a	3.6 a

^a In a column, means followed by the same letter are not different significantly at the 1% level.

Zero, 20, 40, 60, or 80 kg N/ha was applied in 2 equal splits at 20 and 40 d after emergence. Salinity level was monitored throughout the growing period (see figure). N application significantly increased grain yield over that of the control. Eighty and 60 kg N/ha produced highest and similar grain yields (see table). N application also increased plant height, tillers/hill, and panicles/m².

Results suggest that even in saline soils modern varieties respond to increased N levels. □

Electrical conductivity of soil of the experimental applied N field during the growing period, BRRI.